

Synthesis of some *N*-Substituted-benzenepropanamines

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Some *N*-substituted-*m*-ethoxy-*p*-methoxy-2-methylbenzenepropanamines (8) have been synthesised by the condensation of corresponding benzenepropanoyl chlorides with aliphatic and aromatic amines followed by reduction of the resultant amides with LAH. The amine hydrochlorides have been tested *in vitro* for their amebicidal activity against *E. histolytica*.

KEEPING in view the fact that a large number of benzenealkanamines are associated with diverse physiological activities, such as antihistaminic, antihypertensive, analgesic, antiamebic activity¹⁻⁴ etc., some *N*-substituted-benzenepropanamines have been prepared. It was proper to prepare secondary amines by making appropriate substitutions on the *N*-atoms of the primary amines resulting in the formation of compounds which show greater activity⁵ and perhaps less toxicity as these would render the nitrogen atom secondary. In this we report the synthesis of some *N*-alkyl/aryl-5-ethoxy-4-methoxy-2-methyl benzenepropanamines following Scheme 1.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The ¹H nmr spectra was recorded with TMS as internal standard.

Vanillin (1) was first reduced by Clemmensen reduction to get the creosol (2), which was ethylated by refluxing with diethylsulphate (1.1 mol) and ignited K₂CO₃ (2 mol) in dry acetone for 3 h to get 4-ethoxy-3-methoxytoluene (3).

5-Ethoxy-4-methoxy-2-methylbenzaldehyde (4) : It was prepared by making use of Gattermann aldehyde synthesis (Found : C, 68.40 ; H, 7.31. C₁₁H₁₄O₃ requires C, 68.04 ; H, 7.20%).

5-Ethoxy-4-methoxy-2-methylcinnamic acid (5) : 4 (0.1 mol) was converted into the corresponding cinnamic acid (5) by Knoevengel reaction involving condensation with malonic acid (0.16 mol), dry pyridine (50 ml) as solvent and piperidine (0.5 ml) as catalyst. The product (5) was crystallised from aqueous ethanol as a light yellow solid, m.p. 151° (Found : C, 66.34 ; H, 6.65. C₁₈H₁₆O₄ requires C, 66.10 ; H, 6.78%).

5-Ethoxy-4-methoxy-2-methylbenzenepropanoic acid (6) : It was obtained by reducing 5 using Na/Hg as the reducing agent in the usual manner. The product (6) was crystallised from aqueous ethanol as a white solid, m.p. 145° (Found : C,

a^vR = *n*-Hexyl
b: R = *n*-Butyl
c R = Benzyl
d R = 2-Phenylethyl
e R = *p*-Methoxyphenyl

Scheme 1

65.88 ; H, 7.68. C₁₈H₁₈O₄ requires C, 65.54 ; H, 7.56%).

N-Substituted-5-ethoxy-4-methoxy-2-methylbenzenepropanamides (7) : 6 (0.1 mol) was dissolved in dry benzene (25 ml) and the solution refluxed with distilled SOCl₂ (0.15 mol) under anhydrous

condition for 30 min. Excess of SOCl_2 was then removed under reduced pressure, and the resulting acid chloride was cooled, diluted with dry benzene and treated with the appropriate amine (0.1 mol). The mixture was refluxed for 30 min, then cooled, washed successively with NaHCO_3 solution and 6% HCl and dried over anhydrous CaCl_2 . The benzene was removed and the solid crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether to yield the product: **7a**, m.p. $70-71^\circ$ (Found: C, 71.40; H, 9.76; N, 4.45. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{31}\text{O}_3\text{N}$ requires C, 71.03; H, 9.66; N, 4.37%); **7b**, m.p. $82-83^\circ$ (Found: C, 70.02; H, 9.32; N, 4.91. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{25}\text{O}_3\text{N}$ requires C, 69.62; H, 9.21; N, 4.81%); **7c**, m.p. $93-94^\circ$ (Found: C, 73.93; H, 8.10; N, 4.36. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{25}\text{O}_3\text{N}$ requires C, 73.40; H, 7.95; N, 4.27%); **7d**, m.p. $90-91^\circ$ (Found: C, 73.67; H, 7.84; N, 4.01. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{27}\text{O}_3\text{N}$ requires C, 73.90; H, 7.92; N, 4.09%); **7e**, m.p. $89-90^\circ$ (Found: C, 69.65; H, 7.20; N, 4.10. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{25}\text{O}_4\text{N}$ requires C, 69.97; H, 7.29; N, 4.08%).

N-Substituted-5-ethoxy-4-methoxy-2-methylbenzenepropanamine hydrochlorides (**8**): **7** (0.1 mol) in dry ether was added to a slurry of LAH in dry ether, at such a rate that the solvent refluxed gently. The addition was completed in 0.5 h and the resulting mixture warmed on a water-bath for 2-3 h and left overnight. Excess of LAH was destroyed by dropwise addition of 15% NaOH solution. The ethereal layer was dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and KOH. Dry HCl gas was passed through the ethereal solution when amine hydrochloride separated as a white solid, which was filtered, washed with dry ether and recrystallised from methanol-petroleum ether to yield the product: **8a**, m.p. $102-103^\circ$ (Found: C, 66.61; H, 9.98; N, 4.18. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_2\text{NCl}$ requires C, 66.37; H, 9.90; N, 4.10%); **8b**, m.p. $98-99^\circ$ (Found: C, 64.87; H,

9.76; N, 4.66. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_2\text{NCl}$ requires C, 64.34; H, 9.83; N, 4.55%); **8c**, m.p. $107-108^\circ$ (Found: C, 68.94; H, 8.14; N, 4.12. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_2\text{NCl}$ requires C, 68.64; H, 8.10; N, 4.02%); **8d**, m.p. $95-96^\circ$ (Found: C, 69.04; H, 8.36; N, 3.90. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_2\text{NCl}$ requires C, 69.32; H, 8.25; N, 3.85%); **8e**, m.p. $105-106^\circ$ (Found: C, 65.35; H, 7.60; N, 3.89. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_3\text{NCl}$ requires C, 65.66; H, 7.66; N, 3.83%). Moreover, the structures of all the above compounds have been confirmed with the help of uv, ir and nmr spectral data.

Pharmacological evaluation: Aqueous solutions of the amine hydrochlorides (**8**) were tested *in vitro* against axenically grown *E. histolytica* at pH 7.2-7.4. The amebicidal end-point of compounds **8a-e** were found to be 250, 500, 250, 125 and 500 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, respectively. The compounds exhibited very mild to moderate amebicidal activity as compared with the standard drug emetine, whose amebicidal end-point is $15.6 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$.

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